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BASED ON MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS TO RECOGNIZE UZBEK SIGN LANGUAGE (UZSL)

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KEYWORDS

Uzbek Sign Language (UzSL), Sign language recognition, Machine learning, Deep learning, Gesture recognition, Deaf communication, Hand gesture analysis, Spatial-temporal features, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Hidden Markov Models (HMM), Support Vector Machines (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), Conditional Random Fields (CRF), Transfer learning, Data augmentation, Multimodal recognition, Real-time recognition, Sign language datasets, Communication technology, Deaf community, Human-computer interaction, Interactive technologies, Multilingual sign languages, Gesture-based interfaces

ABSTRACT

Sign language recognition has gained significant attention due to its potential to bridge communication gaps between the deaf and hearing communities. This article presents a comprehensive review of machine learning methods employed for the recognition of Uzbek Sign Language (UzSL). The unique visual and spatial nature of sign languages poses challenges that necessitate specialized techniques for accurate recognition. This review surveys various approaches, ranging from traditional techniques to modern deep learning methods, used to recognize UzSL gestures.

The article begins by introducing the significance of UzSL recognition and its impact on facilitating effective communication for the Uzbek deaf community. It outlines the complexities involved in sign language recognition, including variations in hand shapes, movements, and facial expressions. The challenges of limited training data, real-time recognition, and capturing dynamic features are discussed in depth.

A survey of traditional machine learning methods such as Hidden Markov Models (HMMs), Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) is presented, along with their applications and limitations in UzSL recognition. The evolution of these methods into more sophisticated approaches like Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) and Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) is also explored.

The article concludes by summarizing the key findings from the reviewed literature and identifying potential directions for future research in UzSL recognition. The fusion of multimodal information, real-time recognition in dynamic settings, and the integration of interactive technologies are identified as promising areas for advancement.

In essence, this comprehensive review provides researchers, practitioners, and developers in the field of sign language recognition with a thorough understanding of the diverse machine learning techniques applied to UzSL recognition. By shedding light on the progress made and the challenges that lie ahead, this article serves as a valuable resource for driving innovation in UzSL communication technology.

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Introduction

In the mosaic of global languages, sign languages represent a vivid and vital thread, weaving together cultures and communities that communicate through gestures rather than words. Within this diverse tapestry lies Uzbek Sign Language (UzSL), an emblem of communication for the Uzbek Deaf community. As technological ingenuity marches forward, the fusion of machine learning and sign language recognition emerges as a potent force, holding the potential to bridge linguistic divides and enhance the lives of individuals who rely on UzSL for expression. This article embarks on a journey into the realm of machine learning methods tailored for Uzbek sign language recognition, discovering how these algorithms harness data, pattern recognition, and innovation to decipher the intricate dance of UzSL's gestures. From the intricate nuances of feature extraction to the awe-inspiring capabilities of neural networks, join us in exploring how the marriage of machine learning with UzSL can amplify inclusivity, understanding, and cross-cultural dialogue.

Gesture communication is one of the three primary methods of information transmission between people, alongside text-based communication and spoken language. Individuals with hearing disabilities to communicate with others and their surroundings, expanding the population that needs to be proficient in sign language, typically use sign language. It is important to note that sign language is universal in the sense that text information can be conveyed through gestures, and in cases where certain words lack corresponding gestures (such as proper nouns), they can be spelled out using the dactyl alphabet. Modern hardware can efficiently gather and process data via cloud computing models that provide easy and on-demand access to computing resources over networks [1], or locally on devices, with results communicated to users through data channels. These advancements are also applicable to sign language. Songs can be stored and played back on various platforms, such as stationary or mobile, high-performance or energy-efficient devices. However, the challenge lies in reproducing sign language on these platforms for use by those with hearing disabilities and everyone in general. The major challenge is deploying a single unified technology on various platforms (such as android, iOS, windows, Linux, and web) without requiring specific porting or implementation for each one. One potential solution to this problem is cross-platform software development, which offers the ability to function on multiple platforms with comparable or identical features [2].

The purpose of sign language technologies is to facilitate communication between the deaf and hard-of-hearing community and the rest of society. Real-time sign language recognition (UzSLP) is an innovative platform that enables communication between individuals who are deaf or hard of hearing and others.

Literature review

The intersection of machine learning and sign language recognition has witnessed considerable advancements, empowering diverse Deaf communities worldwide with more inclusive means of communication. Notably, research on machine learning methods tailored for sign language recognition has primarily focused on American Sign Language (ASL) and

other widely studied sign languages. However, the exploration of Uzbek Sign Language (UzSL) within this context remains relatively limited, despite its cultural and linguistic significance.

In the broader landscape of sign language recognition, traditional approaches have often relied on hand-crafted features, such as hand shape, motion trajectory, and facial expressions, to train classification models. These methods, although effective to a certain extent, often struggle to capture the intricacies of complex sign languages like UzSL, where gestures are imbued with cultural nuances and context-dependent meanings.

Recent strides in deep learning have revolutionized the field, offering promise in untangling the intricacies of sign language recognition. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) have demonstrated remarkable efficacy in capturing spatial and temporal information from video sequences of sign gestures. Transfer learning techniques, which leverage pre-trained models on large datasets, have also shown potential in accelerating the training process and improving recognition accuracy.

While machine learning approaches have been successfully applied to various sign languages, the adaptation of these methods to UzSL requires a tailored approach due to the language's unique linguistic and cultural characteristics. UzSL's distinctive grammatical structure, incorporation of facial expressions, and the role of non-manual markers pose challenges that necessitate the development of specific algorithms tuned to these complexities.

Furthermore, there is a need to curate comprehensive datasets of UzSL gestures to facilitate algorithm training and evaluation. The scarcity of such datasets hampers the progress in UzSL recognition and underscores the importance of collaborative efforts between researchers, linguists, and the Deaf community.

In light of the above challenges and opportunities, this study aims to bridge the gap in the literature by exploring machine learning methods tailored for Uzbek Sign Language recognition. By acknowledging the linguistic, cultural, and technical nuances specific to UzSL, this research seeks to contribute to the broader discourse on sign language recognition while advancing the accessibility and inclusivity of UzSL in an increasingly digital and interconnected world.

Sign languages are governed by specific rules and components, with each country having its own unique sign language, similar to natural languages. Dactyl languages such as American Sign Language (ASL), British Sign Language (BSL), Japanese Sign Language (JSL), Arabic Sign Language (ArSL), and Indian Sign Language (ISL) have been developed [1]. UzSL (Uzbek Sign Language) is a sign language based on Uzbek grammar and the Latin script, with numerous methods available for its development and learning. Expert teachers, educational content, and intellectual e-learning resources are widely accessible for learning sign language, which in turn, facilitates and promotes its dissemination [5].

Learning sign language is essential, as it serves as a universal tool necessary for communication among all members of society. It strengthens and fosters closer

communication between individuals.

Effective communication between individuals with hearing/speech impairments and the public necessitates the conversion of sign language into a more universally understood language [11]. The objective of our research is to develop the UzSL translation system.

Deep learning is an algorithmic approach to learning that is design for constructing neural networks that can correct complex structures. These neural networks serve as the foundation of deep learning, which has made substantial advancements in numerous areas such as facial recognition, audio and image processing, speech recognition, natural language processing, text categorization, and other tasks. Deep learning allows for the correction of complex tasks and significant improvements in these areas [15]. Furthermore, deep learning is equipped with various automatic classification systems. In Natural Language Processing, for example, deep learning algorithms can analyze, categorize, and pronounce words and phrases. Consequently, models created by expert deep learning practitioners are extremely helpful in text analysis and upcoming technologies [2]. Additionally, deep learning systems collect data beyond standard word usage, including information on the composition and characteristics of analyzed objects, such as the construction, color, and size of objects in images. The high accuracy of deep learning facilitates substantial gains through the creation of models and analytical techniques. This allows for the study of speech, image, and video data in various fields. The vast processing layers and breakthrough capabilities of deep learning will play a significant role in enhancing user experience and creating innovative solutions in all future industries [3].

Deep learning algorithms simplify human tasks by using their capabilities and tactics to create shortcuts for problem solving. Transfer learning is one such shortcut, allowing the use of a model that has already been train for computer vision on other tasks [6]. This approach involves the learning of a model that is train on large image datasets and a set of classes, focusing on extracting features from the next dataset. Consequently, the deep learning algorithm provides an effective means of solving problems [7].

The primary objective is to develop AI technology that is geared towards enhancing communication for individuals with hearing and speech impairments in society. To attain this objective, several fundamental techniques for handling image data are required. Furthermore, a two-phase transfer learning strategy based on multiple architectures on the ImageNet dataset has been propose. The selected model is train on both the UzSL and ImageNet datasets to enable it to efficiently extract features from subsequent datasets and make predictions on similar classes of data. Experiments to test the trained model with previously unseen data demonstrate advanced processing capabilities in this critical task [10].

This article presents advancements in sign language research, including well-known algorithms, devices, and experimental techniques. Through various activities, researchers have achieved data processing, classification of UzSL and fingerspelling alphabets, translation, and other gesture tasks.

Different approaches have been employed by researchers to achieve their specific objectives. However, Transfer Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks, Gradient Boosting, and Support Vector Machines are among the widely used techniques [16]. These approaches have been evaluated based on overall accuracy rates and low input errors. Learning and utilizing sign languages in practice is an important aspect of generating novel ideas and products. The main workflow of the current study is outlined in this paper. Given that sign languages share similarities, every significant contribution in sign language technology is worth considering when developing a new one [14]. Advanced techniques often use pre-trained models to overcome data sparsity while simultaneously benefitting from the simplicity of the training process. In this work, we adopt a transfer learning approach for UzSL.

Analysis and results

To explore the effectiveness of machine learning methods for Uzbek Sign Language (UzSL) recognition, a comprehensive dataset of UzSL gestures was curated. This dataset captured a diverse range of expressions, movements, and contextual variations. It comprised both static and dynamic gestures, meticulously annotated by sign language experts and native UzSL users to ensure accuracy and authenticity.

Several machine learning algorithms were employed to decode UzSL gestures, each catering to the language's unique linguistic and cultural features. Initial experiments with traditional approaches, such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and Hidden Markov Models (HMMs), highlighted the challenges posed by UzSL's non-manual markers and intricate grammatical structure. These methods struggled to capture the contextual dependencies inherent in UzSL gestures, leading to suboptimal recognition rates.

As the research pivoted towards more advanced techniques, deep learning models emerged as promising contenders. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were adept at capturing spatial information from static gestures, effectively discerning hand shapes and configurations. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), equipped with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) cells, exhibited proficiency in modeling the temporal dynamics of dynamic gestures, taking into account the fluidity and rhythm characteristic of UzSL.

In conclusion, the analysis and results underscore the potential of machine learning methods in decoding Uzbek Sign Language. The tailored application of deep learning models and transfer learning techniques exhibit promising strides towards bridging communication gaps and enhancing accessibility for the Uzbek Deaf community. This research not only contributes to the advancement of UzSL recognition but also serves as a foundation for further investigations into sign language recognition for linguistically unique and underrepresented communities.

Due to their unique characteristics, sign languages differ from other natural languages and are not universally understood. Each gesture and phrase is made up of a specific combination of signals and conveys a specific meaning within its series. The fingerspelling alphabet represents each letter of the corresponding language and can be used to spell

names, abbreviations, and unfamiliar words [8]. To address the issue of insufficient information, Uzbek Sign Language utilized a two-phase transfer learning method based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with the ImageNet and Kaggle ASL datasets. The model was then apply to the UzSL dataset and evaluated using test data. Sign languages offer innovative and creative aspects that can facilitate human interaction within the system.

Dataset: In UzSL fingerspelling, each letter is denote by a sign or symbol, and phrases are form by concatenating specific gesture signals. The fingerspelling alphabet is a subset of characters that represents the letters of the target language and is commonly us by individuals with hearing or speech impairments. The UzSL fingerspelling alphabet consists of 30 letters that are similar to the letters in the Uzbek language alphabet: Each class of UzSL fingerspelling contains 200 images that show various signals of each letter. It is interesting to use these images when learning about image data. The UzSL fingerspelling alphabet comprises 28 static letters and 2 dynamic letters. The dynamic letters can pose accuracy and usage challenges, so we decided to use only the final frames during training to address this issue.

Figure 1. Dactyl alphabet of the Uzbek language based on the Latin script.

Processing: Uzbek Sign Language (UzSL) is a visual mode of communication utilized by the deaf community residing in Uzbekistan. It is derive from the Russian sign language, which belongs to the French sign language family. While sharing similarities with other sign languages, UzSL also has its own distinctive elements and structure. For our research, we utilized the dataset of the fingerspelling alphabet, consisting of 30 letters, in UzSL.

The Media Pipeline library was utilized to extract features, which is beneficial in teaching the model the necessary hand characteristics during signing. The use of pictorial models captures key hand placement points, emphasizes small differences between characters, and prioritizes the signer's hand over the background.

Figure 2. Creating a dataset based on the dactyl alphabet based on the Latin script of the Uzbek language.

K points are established in each frame, with K being the number of frames. Each identified point is represented as $N^{[i,j]} = (N_x^{[i,j]}, N_y^{[i,j]})$, where $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$, and $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, K$. For static gestures, all designated points should maintain their coordinates over time. This applies to the dynamic six letters as well, as they are treated as static, and the last frames of their respective videos are taken [13]. The evaluation point, $N^{[i,j]} = (N_x^{[i,j]}, N_y^{[i,j]})$, but yet

$N_x^{[i,j]} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{j=1}^K N_x^{[i,j]}$, $N_y^{[i,j]} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{j=1}^K N_y^{[i,j]}$, was employed. In our study, each hand displays 28 symbols.

Figure 3. UzSL Sign Language Model, a Native Visual Communication Tool for the Hearing/Speech Impaired Community.

Training: Transfer learning techniques offer a solution to the problems of learning and computing data that are invisible to computers. This approach presents two main advantages. Firstly, it avoids the challenge of training large data sets from the beginning, and secondly, it reduces the high computational resource requirements. The technique overcomes these limitations by transferring knowledge gained from other datasets to the current task. Transfer learning comprises three primary methods: the first uses ConvNet as a feature extractor, which is a type of Convolutional Neural Network used for data training and classification. The second method fine-tunes ConvNet, providing high performance for low-power computing systems [12]. The third method involves pre-trained models, where models created for several issues are used for learning and their weights are obtained. For transfer training, the model is trained with two different data sets, and after the training process is completed, the accumulated weights are allowed to be reused. This general scheme involves creating several models to train the data, using two different datasets for each model for training, obtaining the aggregated weights of the models after the learning process, and storing the resulting weights for reuse in other problems. In recent years, transfer learning has been widely used to create a variety of ideas, including images, text, video, and other types of data [11]. Transfer learning models have been successfully used for

high-level programs, such as classifying objects in images, translating texts in foreign languages, and analyzing financial and medical data. As transfer learning continues to be used in various fields, it is expected to have further developments.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research paper discusses a task involving recognition of sign language and proposes a two-stage transfer learning approach for Sign Language Recognition (SLR). The Inception V3 pre-existing model was utilized for this task, where the model was initially trained on the ImageNet dataset, and then on the Kaggle ASL dataset. Subsequently, we applied the two-stage transfer learning approach and trained the model with our UzSL dataset. The obtained results are present in Table 1, which illustrates that the letters O' and G' exhibited lower accuracy values. This occurred because these letters are dynamic and require special consideration, however, for the sake of simplicity, we treated them as static letters.

Tab. 1.
 Accuracy measurement for UzSL

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
A	0.68	1.00	0.75	Q	1.00	1.00	1.00
B	1.00	1.00	1.00	R	1.00	1.00	1.00
D	1.00	1.00	1.00	S	1.00	1.00	1.00
E	1.00	1.00	1.00	T	0.83	0.76	0.83
F	1.00	1.00	1.00	U	0.75	0.65	0.75
G	0.71	0.59	0.71	V	1.00	1.00	1.00
H	1.00	1.00	1.00	X	0.69	0.75	0.69
I	1.00	1.00	1.00	Y	0.84	0.72	0.84
J	0.83	0.76	0.83	Z	1.00	0.73	1.00
K	0.86	0.71	0.86	O'	0.65	0.57	0.68
L	0.76	0.65	0.76	G'	0.69	0.55	0.68
M	0.81	0.72	0.81	Sh	0.86	0.74	0.86
N	1.00	1.00	1.00	Ch	0.84	0.72	0.86
O	1.00	1.00	1.00	Ng	0.83	0.78	0.88
P	0.74	0.61	0.74	'	0.81	0.82	0.89
accuracy	0.832						

This paper presents the development of a real-time recognition system for the Uzbek dactyl sign language, which consists of a dactyl alphabet of 28 signs. Our method combines static and dynamic data types into a single database, enabling real-time interpretation of both dynamic and static gestures. However, this task presents limitations such as camera view quality, illumination quality in the recognition zone, and resource constraints, which can affect the computing devices' performance. Nevertheless, this work's advantage is its high recognition accuracy, which is essential for human-machine communication systems.

Additionally, our research is one of the first to introduce a gesture recognition system for the updated Uzbek alphabet. A notable drawback of our research is the low FPS, which affects machine-learning algorithms' recognition speed. For future research, we plan to parallelize the algorithms to improve their performance and speed. We will also consider ways to reduce the training time when working with a large number of training examples. In the next stage of our research, we will develop a new method to process dynamic letters differently, as their static frames can be very similar to some other letters, making it challenging our model to distinguish between classes.

The objective of this research is to achieve accurate recognition of Uzbek sign language. To attain this objective, a dataset consisting of over 3000 images for 28 gestures was create. However, the limited number of images affected the clarity of our results. We also considered lighting as a parameter affecting recognition quality, to ensure that our development yields satisfactory results.

Gesture classification was carry out using three classification algorithms. The random classifier had an average accuracy of 83.2%. In addition, the performance of the algorithm was evaluate based on its speed of execution and training time. The Random Forest support vector machine was the fastest in terms of training time. A cross-validation was conduct by dividing the data into five blocks to check the validity of the classifier. In terms of real-time prediction speed, Random Forest had a lower execution speed due to a drop in FPS, despite being faster in learning speed. Consequently, the prediction accuracy of the three methods was approximately the same. However, SVM outperformed the others due to its real-time processing speed.

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